

Appendix A: Observation Protocol

Topic	Questions (Observation focus)
Time	When does the meeting start? When does the meeting end?
Meeting environment	Physical/ online/ hybrid
Participants	What are the roles and other details of the participants? <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Number of attendees & their roles- Who leads/ facilitates the meeting?- Major tasks conducted by the participants
Activities	What are the various discussions and activities carried out in the meeting? <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Activities discussed related to RE- Challenges discussed related to RE activities.- How do they carry out Re-related activities?
Team members' personality-related observations	How do team members engage/ cooperate with others? Are there any conflicts within the team? How do the team handle these conflicts (if any)? How do they carry out discussions? The nature of the team members Are they interactive/ outgoing/ reserved? Impact on how they carry out work on RE-related activities and overall tasks?
Events	Are there any particular events or anything unanticipated?
Feelings	How is the atmosphere of the meeting?
Closing	How does the meeting end? Is there any post-meeting planned? How does the PM/ lead deal with the conflicts (if any)? Are there any offline chats/ meetings planned?

Appendix B – Personality Test

Section 01: Demographic Information

1) How old are you?

2) How would you describe your gender?

(Male/ Female/ Prefer to self-describe as:/ Prefer not to answer)

3) Country of your residence?

4) What is your highest educational qualification?

5) How many years have you been in the software industry?

6) Is eliciting/ analysing. prioritising/ modelling/ managing software requirements a part of your job? (Yes/ No)

7) How often do you elicit/ analyse/ prioritize/ manage software requirements as a part of your job?

(Almost every day/ Couple of times a week/ Couple of times a month/ Couple of times a year (or very rarely))

8) What is your current job title/ job role?

9) Your current job responsibilities include: (please rate the following based on your involvement): close-ended question with the Likert scale

from “Never” to “Always”.

- Collaborate with the stakeholders to elicit requirements
- Documenting software requirements specifications according to standard templates
- Lead requirements analysis and verification
- Participate in requirements prioritisation
- Manage requirements throughout the project

10) Is there are any other job responsibilities that you involve in apart from the above list, please mention:

Section 02: Personality Assessment

1) This section contains phrases describing people’s behaviours. Please go through the instructions listed above before you rate the phrases. Please indicate to what extent each of the following statements applies to you.

(Rate with the Likert scale from “very inaccurate” to “very accurate”)

- list of 120 statements can be found in the following table.

1. I worry about things	61. I am afraid of many things
2. I make friends easily	62. I avoid contact with others
3. I have a vivid imagination	63. I love to daydream
4. I trust others	64. I trust what people say
5. I complete tasks successfully	65. I handle tasks smoothly
6. I get angry easily	66. I lose my temper
7. I love large parties	67. I prefer to be alone
8. I believe in the importance of art	68. I do not like poetry
9. I use others for my own ends	69. I take advantage of others
10. I like to tidy up	70. I leave a mess in my room
11. I often feel blue	71. I am often down in the dumps
12. I take charge	72. I take control of things
13. I experience my emotions intensely	73. I rarely notice my emotional reactions
14. I love to help others	74. I am indifferent to the feeling of others
15. I keep my promises	75. I break rules
16. I find it difficult to approach others	76. I only feel comfortable with friends
17. I am always busy	77. I do a lot in my spare time
18. I prefer a variety of routine	78. I dislike changes
19. I love a good fight	79. I insult people
20. I work hard	80. I do just enough work to get by
21. I go on binges	81. I easily resist temptations
22. I love excitement	82. I enjoy being reckless
23. I love to read challenging materials	83. I have difficulty understanding abstract ideas
24. I believe that I am better than others	84. I have a high opinion of myself
25. I am always prepared	85. I waste my time
26. I panic easily	86. I feel that I'm unable to deal with things
27. I radiate joy	87. I love life
28. I tend to vote for liberal political candidates	88. I tend to vote for conservative political candidates
29. I sympathise with the homeless	89. I am not interested in other people's problems
30. I jump into things without thinking	90. I rush into things
31. I fear for the worst	91. I get stressed out easily
32. I feel comfortable around people	92. I keep others at a distance
33. I enjoy wild flights of fantasy	93. I like to get lost in thought
34. I believe that others have good intentions	94. I distrust people
35. I excel in what I do	95. I know how to get things done
36. I get irritated easily	96. I am not easily annoyed
37. I talk to a lot of different people at parties	97. I avoid crowds
38. I see beauty in the things that others might not notice	98. I do not enjoy going to art museums
39. I cheat to get ahead	99. I obstruct others' plans
40. I often forgot to put things back in their proper place	100. I leave my belongings around

41. I dislike myself	101. I feel comfortable with myself
42. I try to lead others	102. I wait for others to lead the way
43. I feel others' emotions	103. I don't understand people who get emotional
44. I am concerned about others	104. I take no time for others
45. I tell the truth	105. I break my promises
46. I am afraid to draw attention to myself	106. I am not bothered by difficult social situations
47. I am always on the go	107. I like to take it easy
48. I prefer to stick with the things I know	108. I am attracted to conventional ways
49. I yell at people	109. I get back at others
50. I do more than what's expected of me	110. I put little time and effort into my work
51. I rarely overindulge	111. I am able to control my cravings
52. I seek adventure	112. I act wild and crazy
53. I avoid philosophical discussions	113. I am not interested in theoretical discussions
54. I think highly of myself	114. I boast about my virtues
55. I carry out my plans	115. I have difficulty starting tasks
56. I become overwhelmed by events	116. I remain calm under pressure
57. I have a lot of fun	117. I look at the bright side of life
58. I believe that there is no absolute right or wrong	118. I believe that we should be tough on crime
59. I feel sympathy for those who are worse off than myself	119. I try not to think about the needy
60. I make rash decisions	120. I act without thinking

2) Do you wish to receive your individual personality profile? (Yes/No)

3) If yes, please enter your name and email address

Appendix C – Interview Protocol

Demographic Information

- Can you briefly tell me about yourself?
- Considering your experience, how many years of experience do you have in the software industry?
- How many years of experience do you have in requirement engineering these years?
- Can you think of your current software engineering project where you were engaged in RE activities?
 - Can you please tell me very briefly about that project?
 - What RE-related activities were being performed on that project?
 - What was your involvement in those activities?

Views on the influence of personality in RE-related activities

Explanation: Personality can be simply described as a set of individual differences, including personal habits, skills, memories, behaviours and social relationships that can be affected by the social and cultural development of individuals. There are various personality models that can be used to measure individual personality, and the one you all have used is the Five Factor Model-one of the most used models in this domain. There are five broad dimensions used in common language to describe human personality as follows:

Openness to Experience: Someone who is high on openness to experience tends to appear as imaginative, broad-minded and curious, whereas those at the opposite end of this spectrum prefer routine and favouring conservative values

Conscientiousness: People who are high in conscientiousness tend to be hardworking, organised, able to complete tasks thoroughly and on time, and reliable. On the other hand, low conscientiousness relates to traits such as being irresponsible, impulsive and disordered.

Extraversion: A person is considered an extravert if he/she feels comfortable in a social relationship, friendly, assertive, active and outgoing

Agreeableness: Refers to traits such as cooperativeness, kindness, trust and warm, whereas people who are low on agreeableness tend to be sceptical, selfish and hostile

Neuroticism: Refers to the state of emotional stability. Someone who is low on Neuroticism tends to appear calm, confident and secure, whereas a high neuroticism individual tends to be moody, anxious, nervous and insecure.

Talking about an individual's personality:

- Have you experienced a person's personality having an effect or impact on how they approach requirements engineering?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
 - If not, why do you think it does not have any impact?
- Can you think of a time when your own personality (or your team members') positively influenced how they carried out RE activities?
 - Who else did it impact, and how?
- Can you think of a time when your own personality (or someone's) negatively influenced how they carried out RE activities?
 - Who else did it impact, and how?
- Have you experienced your team members' personalities influencing how they carried out RE activities?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
 - If not, why do you think it does not influence?
- Have you experienced combinations of different personality types impacting RE activities?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
- How do you handle various personality differences within your team?
- In your experience, are there any other human aspects/ human-centric issues that have an impact on performing RE activities?
 - If yes, what are they?
 - How do they impact?
- Any final thoughts about the impact of personality on RE-related activities?

IPIP -NEO Narrative Report – Personality Profile

NOTE: This report is sent to you upon your request, and it is analysed using the standard IPIP-NEO 120 Personality testing tool developed based on the standard Five-Factor Model (FFM) of Personality.

This report estimates the individual's level on each of the five broad personality domains of the Five-Factor Model. The description of each one of the five broad domains is followed by a more detailed description of personality according to the six sub-domains/facets that comprise each domain.

A note on terminology – Personality traits describe, relative to other people, the frequency or intensity of a person's feelings, thoughts, or behaviours. Possession of a trait is, therefore, a matter of degree. We might describe two individuals as "extraverts", but still see one as more extroverted than the other. This report uses expressions such as "extravert" or "high in extraversion" to describe someone who is likely to be seen by others as relatively extraverted. This report is generated based on the analysis of your answers to the personality test and classifies you as low, average, or high in a trait according to whether your score is approximately in the lowest 30%, middle 40% or highest 30% of scores obtained by people of your sex and roughly your age. Your numerical scores are reported and graphs as percentile estimates.

Please keep in mind that "low", "average", and "high" scores on a personality test are neither absolutely good nor bad. A particular level on any trait will probably be neutral or irrelevant for a great many activities, be helpful for accomplishing some things and detrimental for accomplishing other things. As with any personality inventory/tool, scores and descriptions can only approximate an individual's actual personality. High and low-score descriptions are usually accurate, but average scores close to the low or high boundaries might misclassify you as only average. On each set of six sub-domain scales, it is somewhat uncommon but certainly possible to score high in some of the sub-domains and low in others. In such cases, more attention should be paid to the sub-domain scores than the broad domain score. Questions about the accuracy of your results are best resolved by showing your report to people who know you well.

Dr John A. Johnson, the founder of IPIP-NEO 120 personality inventory, wrote the description of the five domains and thirty subdomains. These descriptions are based on extensive reading of the scientific literature on personality measurement. Hence, we would like to acknowledge Dr John A. Johnson for finding and introducing this personality inventory to the public domain.

Extraversion

Extraversion is marked by pronounced engagement with the external world. Extraverts enjoy being with people, are full of energy and often experience positive emotions. They tend to be enthusiastic, action-oriented individuals who are like to say "Yes!" or "let's go!" to opportunities for excitement. In groups, they like to talk, assert themselves and draw attention to themselves.

Introverts lack the exuberance, energy, and activity levels of extroverts. They tend to be quiet, low-key, deliberate and disengaged from the social world. Their lack of social involvement should not be interpreted as shyness or depression. The introvert simply needs less stimulation than an extrovert and prefers to be alone. The independence and reserve of the introvert are sometimes mistaken as unfriendliness or arrogance. In reality, an introvert who scores high on the agreeableness dimension will not seek others out but will be quite pleasant when approached.

Your score on Extraversion is average, indicating you are neither a subdued loner nor a jovial chatterbox. You enjoy time with others, but also time alone.

Extraversion Facets:

- Friendliness (E1) – Friendly people genuinely like other people and openly demonstrate positive feelings toward others. They make friends quickly, and it is easy for them to form close, intimate relationships. Low scorers on Friendliness are not necessarily cold and hostile, but they do not reach out to others and are perceived as distant and reserved. Your level of friendliness is average.
- Gregariousness (E2) – Gregarious people find the company of others pleasantly stimulating and rewarding. They enjoy the excitement of crowds. Low scorers tend to feel overwhelmed by and, therefore, actively avoid large crowds. They do not necessarily dislike being with people sometimes, but their need for privacy and time to themselves is much greater than for individuals who score high on this scale. Your level of gregariousness is low.
- Assertiveness (E3) – High scorers' assertiveness like to speak out, take charge and direct the activities of others. They tend to be leaders in groups. Low scorers tend not to talk much and let others control the activities of groups. Your level of assertiveness is average.
- Activity Level (E4) – Active individuals lead fast-paced, but lives. They move about quickly, energetically, and vigorously and they are involved in many activities. People who score low on this scale follow a slower and more leisurely, relaxed pace. Your activity level is average.
- Excitement-Seeking (E5) – High scorers on this scale are easily bored without high levels of stimulation. They love bright lights and hustle and bustle. They are likely to take risks and seek thrills. Low scorers are overwhelmed by noise and commotion and are averse to thrill-seeking. Your level of excitement-seeking is average.
- Cheerfulness (E6) – This scale measures positive mood and feelings, not negative emotions (which are a part of the Neuroticism domain). Persons who score high on this scale typically experience a range of positive feelings, including happiness, enthusiasm, optimism, and joy. Low scorers are not as prone to such energetic, high spirits. Your level of positive emotions is average.

Agreeableness

Agreeableness reflects individuals' differences in concern with cooperation and social harmony. Agreeable individuals value getting along with others. They are, therefore considerate, friendly, generous, helpful, and willing to compromise their interest with others. Agreeable people also have

an optimistic view of human nature. They believe people are basically honest, decent, and trustworthy.

Disagreeable individuals place self-interest above getting along with others. They are generally unconcerned with others' well-being and therefore are unlikely to extend themselves to other people. Sometimes their skepticism about others' motives causes them to be suspicious, unfriendly, and uncooperative.

Agreeableness is obviously advantageous for attaining and maintaining popularity. Agreeable people are better liked than disagreeable people. On the other hand, agreeableness is not useful in situations that require tough or absolutely objective decisions. Disagreeable people can make excellent scientists, critics, or soldiers.

Your high level of agreeableness indicates a strong interest in others' needs and well-being. You are pleasant, sympathetic, and cooperative.

Agreeableness Facets:

- Trust (A1) – A person with high trust assumes that most people are fair, honest, and have good intentions. Persons low in the trust see others as selfish, devious, and potentially dangerous. Your level of trust is high.
- Morality (A2) – High scorers on this scale see no need for pretence or manipulation when dealing with others and are therefore candid, frank, and sincere. Low scorers believe that a certain amount of deception in social relationships is necessary. People find it relatively easy to relate to the straightforward high scorers on this scale. They generally find it more difficult to relate to the unstraightforward low scorers on this scale. It should be made clear that low scorers are not unprincipled or immoral; they are simply more guarded and less willing to openly reveal the whole truth. Your level of morality is high.
- Altruism (A3) – Altruistic people find helping other people genuinely rewarding. Consequently, they are generally willing to assist those who are in need. Altruistic people find that doing things for others is a form of self-fulfilment rather than self-sacrifice. Low scorers on this scale do not particularly like helping those in need. Requests for help feel like an imposition rather than an opportunity for self-fulfilment. Your level of altruism is high.
- Cooperation (A4) – Individuals who score high on this scale dislike confrontations. They are perfectly willing to compromise or deny their own needs in order to get along with others. Those who score low on this scale are more likely to intimidate others to get their way. Your level of cooperation is high.
- Modesty (A5) – High scorers on this scale do not like to claim that they are better than other people. In some cases, this attitude may derive from low self-confidence or self-esteem.

Nonetheless, some people with high self-esteem find immodesty unseemly. Those who are willing to describe themselves as superior tend to be seen as disagreeably arrogant by other people. Your level of modesty is high.

- Sympathy (A6) – People who score high on this scale are tender-hearted and compassionate. They feel the pain of others vicariously and are easily moved to pity. Low scorers are not affected strongly by human suffering. They pride themselves on making objective judgments based on reason. They are more concerned with truth and impartial justice than with mercy. Your level of tendermindedness is high.

Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness concerns the way in which we control, regulate, and direct our impulses. Impulses are not inherently bad; occasionally, time constraints require a snap decision and acting on our first impulse can be an effective response. Also, in times of play rather than work, acting spontaneously and impulsively can be fun. Impulsive individuals can be seen by others as colourful, fun-to-be-with, and zany.

Nonetheless, acting on impulse can lead to trouble in a number of ways. Some impulses are antisocial. Uncontrolled antisocial acts not only harm other members of society but also can result in retribution toward the perpetrator of such impulsive acts. Another problem with impulsive acts is that they often produce immediate rewards but undesirable, long-term consequences. Examples include excessive socializing that leads to being fired from one's job, hurling an insult that causes the breakup of an important relationship or using pleasure-inducing drugs that eventually destroy one's health.

Impulsive behaviour, even when not seriously destructive, diminishes a person's effectiveness in significant ways. Acting impulsively disallows contemplating alternative courses of action, some of which would have been wiser than the impulsive choice. Impulsivity also side-tracks people during projects that require organized sequences of steps or stages. Accomplishments of an impulsive person are therefore small, scattered, and inconsistent.

A hallmark of intelligence, what potentially separates human beings from earlier life forms, is the ability to think about future consequences before acting on an impulse. Intelligent activity involves contemplation of long-range goals, organizing and planning routes to these goals, and persisting toward one's goals in the face of short-lived impulses to the contrary. The idea that intelligence involves impulse control is nicely captured by the term prudence, an alternative label for the Conscientiousness domain. Prudent means both wise and cautious. Persons who score high on the Conscientiousness scale are, in fact, perceived by others as intelligent.

The benefits of high conscientiousness are obvious. Conscientious individuals avoid trouble and achieve high levels of success through purposeful planning and persistence. They are also positively regarded by others as intelligent and reliable. On the negative side, they can be compulsive perfectionists and workaholics. Furthermore, extremely conscientious individuals might be regarded as stuffy and boring. Unconscientious people may be criticized for their unreliability, lack of ambition, and failure to stay within the lines, but they will experience many short-lived pleasures and they will never be called stuffy.

Your score on conscientiousness is high. This means you set clear goals and pursue them with determination. People regard you as reliable and hard-working.

Conscientiousness Facets:

- Self-Efficacy (C1) – Self-Efficacy describes confidence in one's ability to accomplish things. High scorers believe they have the intelligence (common sense), drive, and self-control necessary for achieving success. Low scorers do not feel effective and may have a sense that they are not in control of their lives. Your level of self-efficacy is high.
- Orderliness (C2) – Persons with high scores on orderliness are well-organized. They like to live according to routines and schedules. They keep lists and make plans. Low scorers tend to be disorganized and scattered. Your level of orderliness is high.
- Dutifulness (C3) – This scale reflects the strength of a person's sense of duty and obligation. Those who score high on this scale have a strong sense of moral obligation. Low scorers find contracts, rules, and regulations overly confining. They are likely to be seen as unreliable or even irresponsible. Your level of dutifulness is high.
- Achievement-Striving (C4) – Individuals who score high on this scale strive hard to achieve excellence. Their drive to be recognized as successful keeps them on track toward their lofty goals. They often have a strong sense of direction in life, but extremely high scores may be too single-minded and obsessed with their work. Low scorers are content to get by with a minimal amount of work and might be seen by others as lazy. Your level of achievement striving is high.
- Self-Discipline (C5) – Self-discipline-what many people call will-power-refers to the ability to persist at difficult or unpleasant tasks until they are completed. People who possess high self-discipline are able to overcome reluctance to begin tasks and stay on track despite distractions. Those with low self-discipline procrastinate and show poor follow-through, often failing to complete tasks-even tasks they want very much to complete. Your level of self-discipline is average.
- Cautiousness (C6) – Cautiousness describes the disposition to think through possibilities before acting. High scorers on the Cautiousness scale take their time when making decisions. Low scorers often say or do the first thing that comes to mind without deliberating about alternatives and the probable consequences of those alternatives. Your level of cautiousness is high.

Neuroticism

Neuroticism refers to the tendency to experience negative feelings. Those who score high on Neuroticism may experience primarily one specific negative feeling such as anxiety, anger, or depression., but are likely to experience several of these emotions. People high in neuroticism are emotionally reactive. They respond emotionally to events that would not affect most people, and their reactions tend to be more intense than normal. They are more likely to interpret ordinary situations as threatening and minor frustrations as hopelessly difficult. Their negative emotional reactions tend to persist for unusually long periods of time, which means they are often in a bad mood. These problems in emotional regulation can diminish a neurotic's ability to think clearly, make decisions, and cope effectively with stress.

At the other end of the scale, individuals who score low in neuroticism are less easily upset and are less emotionally reactive. They tend to be calm, emotionally stable, and free from persistent negative feelings. Freedom from negative feelings does not mean that low scorers experience a lot of positive feelings; the frequency of positive emotions is a component of the Extraversion domain.

Your score on neuroticism is average, indicating that your level of emotional reactivity is typical of the general population. Stressful and frustrating situations are somewhat upsetting to you, but you are generally able to get over these feelings and cope with these situations.

Neuroticism Facets:

- Anxiety (N1) – The "fight-or-flight" system of the brain of anxious individuals is too easily and too often engaged. Therefore, people who are high in anxiety often feel like something dangerous is about to happen. They may be afraid of specific situations or be just generally fearful. They feel tense, jittery, and nervous. Persons low in Anxiety are generally calm and fearless. Your level of anxiety is high.
- Anger (N2) – Persons who score high in Anger feel enraged when things do not go their way. They are sensitive about being treated fairly and feel resentful and bitter when they feel they are being cheated. This scale measures the tendency to feel angry; whether or not the person expresses annoyance and hostility depends on the individual's level of Agreeableness. Low scorers do not get angry often or easily. Your level of anger is low.
- Depression (N3) – This scale measures the tendency to feel sad, dejected, and discouraged. High scorers lack energy and have difficulty initiating activities. Low scorers tend to be free from these depressive feelings. Your level of depression is average.
- Self-Consciousness (N4) – Self-conscious individuals are sensitive about what others think of them. Their concern about rejection and ridicule causes them to feel shy and uncomfortable around others. They are easily embarrassed and often feel ashamed. Their fears that others

will criticize or make fun of them are exaggerated and unrealistic, but their awkwardness and discomfort may make these fears a self-fulfilling prophecy. Low scorers, in contrast, do not suffer from the mistaken impression that everyone is watching and judging them. They do not feel nervous in social situations. Your level of self-consciousness is high.

- Immoderation (N5) – Immoderate individuals feel strong cravings and urge that they have difficulty resisting. They tend to be oriented toward short-term pleasures and rewards rather than long-term consequences. Low scorers do not experience strong, irresistible cravings and consequently do not find themselves tempted to overindulge. Your level of immoderation is average.
- Vulnerability (N6) – High scorers on Vulnerability experience panic, confusion, and helplessness when under pressure or stress. Low scorers feel more poised, confident, and clear-thinking when stressed. Your level of vulnerability is average.

Openness to Experience

Openness to Experience describes a dimension of cognitive style that distinguishes imaginative, creative people from down-to-earth, conventional people. Open people are intellectually curious, appreciative of art and sensitive to beauty. They tend to be, compared to closed people, more aware of their feelings. They tend to think and act in individualistic and nonconforming ways. Intellectuals typically score high on Openness to Experience; consequently, this factor has also been called Culture or Intellect. Nonetheless, Intellect is probably best regarded as one aspect of openness to experience. Scores on Openness to Experience are only modestly related to years of education and scores on standard intelligent tests.

Another characteristic of the open cognitive style is a facility for thinking in symbols and abstractions far removed from concrete experience. Depending on the individual's specific intellectual abilities, this symbolic cognition may take the form of mathematical, logical, or geometric thinking, artistic and metaphorical use of language, music composition or performance, or one of the many visual or performing arts. People with low scores on openness to experience tend to have narrow, common interests. They prefer the plain, straightforward, and obvious over the complex, ambiguous, and subtle. They may regard the arts and sciences with suspicion regarding these endeavours as abstruse or of no practical use. Closed people prefer familiarity over novelty; they are conservative and resistant to change.

Openness is often presented as healthier or more mature by psychologists, who are often themselves open to experience. However, open and closed styles of thinking are useful in different environments. The intellectual style of the open person may serve a professor well, but research has shown that closed thinking is related to superior job performance in police work, sales, and a number of service occupations.

Your score on Openness to Experience is average, indicating you enjoy tradition but are willing to try new things. Your thinking is neither simple nor complex. To others, you appear to be a well-educated person.

Openness Facets:

- Imagination (O) – To imaginative individuals, the real world is often too plain and ordinary. High scorers on this scale use fantasy as a way of creating a richer, more interesting world. Low scorers on this scale are more oriented to facts than fantasy. Your level of imagination is high.
- Artistic Interests (O2) – High scorers on this scale love beauty, both in art and in nature. They become easily involved and absorbed in artistic and natural events. They are not necessarily artistically trained or talented, although many will be. The defining features of this scale are interest in, and appreciation of natural and artificial beauty. Low scorers lack aesthetic sensitivity and interest in the arts. Your level of artistic interest is high.
- Emotionality (O3) – Persons high on Emotionality have good access to and awareness of their own feelings. Low scorers are less aware of their feelings and tend not to express their emotions openly. Your level of emotionality is high.
- Adventurousness (O4) – High scorers on adventurousness are eager to try new activities, travel to foreign lands, and experience different things. They find familiarity and routine boring and will take a new route home just because it is different. Low scorers tend to feel uncomfortable with change and prefer familiar routines. Your level of adventurousness is average.
- Intellect (O5) – Intellect and artistic interests are the two most important, central aspects of openness to experience. High scorers on Intellect love to play with ideas. They are open-minded to new and unusual ideas and like to debate intellectual issues. They enjoy riddles, puzzles, and brain teasers. Low scorers on Intellect prefer dealing with either people or things rather than ideas. They regard intellectual exercises as a waste of time. Intellect should not be equated with intelligence. Intellect is an intellectual style, not an intellectual ability, although high scorers on Intellect score slightly higher than low-Intellect individuals on standardized intelligence tests. Your level of intellect is average.
- Liberalism (O6) – Psychological liberalism refers to a readiness to challenge authority, convention, and traditional values. In its most extreme form, psychological liberalism can even represent outright hostility toward rules, sympathy for lawbreakers, and love of ambiguity, chaos, and disorder. Psychological conservatives prefer the security and stability brought by conformity to tradition. Psychological liberalism and conservatism are not identical to political affiliation but certainly, incline individuals toward certain political parties. Your level of liberalism is high.

Appendix E: Sample of the code book for “Collaborative nature in managing requirements changes”

	Raw data	Code	Concept	Category
Meeting 01	<p>P3: Well. Do you mind if I request you to work with P4 on this one day?</p> <p>P8: Yep, we are going to have a look at it definitely. (for P4), let’s plan a time for both of us.</p> <p>P4: Awesome.</p>	Cooperation (among team)	<p align="center">Collaboration work (to complete changes)</p>	<p align="center">Collaborative nature in managing requirements changes</p>
Meeting 04	<p>P5: I’m wrapping up the testing for ... part. By the end of this week, it should be done. So, (for P8), can we plan the integration next week? Are you ok with that?</p> <p>P8: Probably somewhere around next Wednesday would be fine.</p>	Working together to complete task		
Meeting 06	<p>P3: I think we can definitely talk about this with the product owner and see what he says, and if yes, this can be incorporated, then probably we'll have to look at the priority in a different manner as long as the product owner and the team are happy. So, is there any team collaboration that we need for this work? Or is this just more like something that the front and developers want to keep in?</p> <p>P9: we might want to go through them at the storytime. <i>Then maybe we can decide. I am happy to work on it.</i></p>	Providing support to do changes (for the team)		
Meeting 15	<p>P2: There are two stories that we need to focus on. (P1), informed about this after his meeting with (X stakeholder).</p> <p>P10: The other one, 2550 one, I started working on it. I am also testing some cases with P8 and P9. I think we can look into that as well.</p> <p>P8: Let’s begin the preparation for the X feature as well (to P10); what do you say? I’m also working on the automation piece in the background; I can work on it with you</p> <p>P10: Yep, then we can have a look at it definitely and see how it goes. I think we can work on it</p>	Collaborative work (to complete added tasks)		
Meeting 18	<p>P1: The other issue (to P10), correct me if I’m wrong, but with the (feature Y), we are still doing sample testing, right? The (X stakeholder) has not released the (data) yet.</p> <p>P10: Yes, not yet</p> <p>P1: I don’t really want to cancel it because you have already made the change as they wanted. But we have been trying to get them. It will be more pain to keep it last.</p>	Support to keep the changes		

	<p>P3: I will talk to them today to get (data) soon.</p> <p>P1: Great (to P8); just keep it to change the values. Make sure that it functions right or just leave it until we get the (data)</p> <p>P8: Okay, thanks (to P3), we can work on it after your update then</p>			
Meeting 19	<p>P11: This is related to 2905; I ran a test yesterday. It was successful. But with the new XXX allocation and integration (to P8 & P9), can you make one more run today? Then, we will see how we go with that.</p> <p>P8: (to P11), yes, we can do it in our meeting after this one. Sounds good? (to P9), can you join? It's XXX allocation validation. It's basically testing these two things together.</p> <p>P9: Yes, But I have a discussion with P1 after this meeting. I can go through it after this.</p> <p>P8: Okay, we can discuss it later today then.</p>	Cooperative to complete tasks		
Meeting 22	<p>P9: On 2549, I further need some help to progress. P2 and I discussed this earlier. (to P10), will be able to have a look at it? It is this XX part that we had to add in the last sprint.</p> <p>P10: Yep, I think we (mentioning P4) did that part. When do you want it to be done (P9)?</p> <p>P9: By tomorrow?</p> <p>P10: I'll try, (to P1), do we have an ETA from (X stakeholder) about when will that they probably be able to send the (data)? If it is going to be late, I can work on this with P9 today.</p> <p>P1: Not yet, it's taking time, I guess</p> <p>P10: Okay, please let me know</p>	Support others to complete new changes		
Meeting 23	<p>P1: While we are talking about 2551, make sure not to mix it up with the request of the validation in back end (XXX feature). Based on the time in this sprint, we can move it to the next sprint.</p> <p>P4: Could we keep it as it is at the moment?</p> <p>P1: Yes, we are not touching that at all. It will take more time. For the next sprint, I want (P10, P4 & P5) to have a closer look at it. If not just keep it.</p> <p>P10: We are going to add (name) allocation anyway. Lots of stuff is there to do. We can look at it while doing that, of course in the next sprint.</p> <p>P4: Yes, it is just that we need to use the schedule properly, without repeating. I think we might be able to do it just by changing (anonymised).</p>	Collaboration work on new tasks		

Meeting 26	<p>P1: Someone will bring this up in the next (stakeholder) meeting. We need to get this resolved.</p> <p>P2: Yes, I can do that. It is (stakeholder) who requested this. I think we need to talk to them.</p> <p>P9: So the (data) will be changed, right? Could I test with the current data we have? Or else, I have to put this on hold and I think we are missing the start of testing everything end to end</p> <p>P1: Yes, yesterday P8 and I worked on the front end part to the back end enhancement. So what was happening was that our errors were not detailed enough to see what was wrong with the changes.</p> <p>P2: In the integration piece, there was a missing element in the sessional locations response. I think that little minor things that help us improve the ratio between UI and the back end.</p> <p>P8: I think we are missing that because we are missing that story. We have to work on the issues of this change to make the integration smooth. So, I guess it'd be great if I work with P2, and P9 on this within next couple of days.</p> <p>P9: I agree. We have to prioritize this</p>	Collaborative work to solve the issues (on changes)		
P1/INT01	<p>"I can think of one example. Generally, junior members tend to observe and learn. But whenever there are new changes to be made, which are difficult to handle, they want someone's support to work on it. I think there are couple of people in my team, who understand this and they are always offer their support to solve it. I think it is because of their nature"</p>	Nature of working together (to make changes)		
P2/INT02	<p>"There are a couple of factors I think are important. Specifically, the cooperation among team members, I have seen in our team that most of them are very helpful to each other. I joined the team as a junior member, and they helped me a lot when dealing with different requests from (anonymised) and then changing our sprint plans accordingly."</p>	Cooperative team members		
P3/INT03	<p>"I think it is really helpful to have cooperative team members when we prioritize the requirements and handle requirement changes in a later phase. In the end, it is all about teamwork"</p>	Cooperative team members in handling changes		

P4/INT04	"I have seen how engaging my team members are. When it is more engaging, it is more fun, effective and you don't feel the difficulties. It's like we'll go through it. Whether it is deadlines, change requests, or anything, as a team coming up with solutions together. Having such team members make the difference"	Engaging team members		
P7/INT06	"There was a person who was working on time, you know, only eight to five working hours, he is not picking any phone calls after that. But, when he works, he is very efficient; he knows how to work with others, complete the tasks beforehand and even handle most of the changes. I think that his organizing and cooperative traits are really helpful"	Cooperative trait of the team member		

Sample of a memo on "Collaborative nature of Team members"

During the meetings, P8 and P10 seem to have mostly engaged with team members compared to others. They always work together and even mostly with P9. Among the follow-up interview participants, the majority (n=5) talked about the collaborative nature and how it is helpful in completing their tasks. This is specifically observed in the meetings when they are discussing new user stories, changes they have to make or testing the changes they made. They refer to it as "supportive team members", "cooperation", "working together", and "coping with others", which emphasise the collaborative nature of the individual. This can be identified as a personality-related characteristic. In the follow-up interview, P1, P2, P3, P4 and P6 discussed this and highlighted that their collaborative nature positively impacted their task completion, specifically working on requirements changes. However, it would be great to know their opinion from P8 and P10, who seem to be highly collaborative but who did not participate in our follow-up interviews.